

Effectiveness of Digital Maternal Health Messages in improving Women's Knowledge of Maternal Health Issues

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Abstract

This paper examines the effectiveness of digital maternal health messages in improving women's knowledge of maternal health issues. The study adopted a library research design and relied on secondary data obtained from books, journal articles, reports and other scholarly publications relevant to digital health communication and maternal health education. A thematic method of analysis was used to analyse the reviewed literature. Findings from the reviewed studies indicate that exposure to digital maternal health messages can significantly enhance women's awareness and understanding of maternal health practices, including antenatal care attendance, recognition of pregnancy danger signs and utilisation of maternal healthcare services. However, the effectiveness of digital maternal health communication may be influenced by factors such as digital literacy, technological access and socio-cultural considerations. The study concludes that digital maternal health communication has the potential to improve women's knowledge of maternal health issues when properly designed and effectively implemented.

Keywords: Digital Communication, Maternal Health Messages, Maternal Health Knowledge, Digital Health Communication, Maternal Health Education, Women's Health Awareness

Introduction

The maternal health is a critical area of the public health and sustainable development in the world more so in the developing countries where maternal mortality and morbidity is a major issue. Maternal health can be defined as health of pregnant women, childbirth and post partum and includes the medical care, nutritional provision and health education needed to achieve safe motherhood (Ope, 2020). Although there are international efforts in an effort to enhance maternal health outcomes, the developing countries still register a high number of challenges in terms of poor access to maternal healthcare services and poor knowledge of maternal health practices among women.

In Nigeria and most of the sub-Saharan Africa, the maternal health outcome does not only depend on availability of healthcare services but also on the awareness and the knowledge of maternal health problems among women. The information on antenatal care, safe delivery methods, prenatal nutrition, and postnatal health is also worthwhile in

defining maternal health behaviour. It has also been found that exposure to health information via the mass media is a significant element of enhancing maternal health awareness in women. As an example, Igbinoba *et al* (2020) note that women with continuous exposure to health information in the media are more likely to exhibit high rates of awareness about maternal health practices than women who are not exposed.

Communication hence is a key in the development of health awareness and behaviour within the society. Asemah (2021) claims that communication is a potent tool to share information, shape the perception of the population and promote behaviour change concerning health and social matters. With proper communication strategies, health institutions and other development organisations can access various audiences with information that can change their knowledge, attitudes and practices. Using communication-based interventions application is becoming more popular in the context of maternal health whereby women are provided with pertinent information that can inform their health choices during, before and after pregnancy.

The intensive development of digital technologies has reshaped the situation in health communication greatly. The digital communication platforms like mobile phones, social media, mobile health application and other online platforms have become significant channels in which health information can be communicated to masses. The technologies are an avenue to availability of timely, accessible and interactive spread of health information especially in areas where traditional health communication channels might not be as broadly available. Consequently, digital health communication has become a significant part of maternal health education programme in most developing nations.

Digital maternal health messaging is using digital devices such as mobile text messages, health applications, social media platforms and other electronic communication platforms to provide information pertaining to pregnancy care, maternal nutrition, antenatal services, danger signs during pregnancy and postnatal care. These digital interventions are aimed at enabling women to have the information required to make informed choices concerning their health and the wellbeing of their unborn. In their systematic review of the digital maternal health education interventions in low-infrastructure settings, Mustapha *et al* (2021) state that digital communication tools have already shown a high potential in enhancing maternal health knowledge in women, especially in those regions where access to traditional healthcare information could be low.

Likewise, online patient education has also become a widely recognised intervention strategy in terms of improving maternal health awareness and motivation in pregnant women. Schnitman *et al* (2022) note that with the help of digital health education platforms, women are able to get access to maternal health information in a convenient way and, thus, enhance their knowledge of pregnancy-related problems and empower them to make better decisions during pregnancy and childbirth. The latter digital communication tools also help provide sustained contact between health providers

and expectant mothers with the help of reminding, educational messages and interactive communication channels.

Moreover, current research highlights the significance of conceptualising maternal health communication strategies that are based on lived experiences and information requirements of women. Sampson *et al* (2022) also claim that proper perinatal health communication need to focus on the voices and opinions of mothers, especially those who may face the risk of maternal mortality and morbidity. Communication interventions can enhance the knowledge of women on maternal health issues and adopt positive health behaviours by modifying the maternal health messages according to the specific concerns and socio-cultural realities of the women.

Although the use of digital communication strategies has been on the rise in the area of maternal health education, it is still important to critically review its success in enhancing women knowledge of maternal health issues. Although the digital platform presents the benefit of a large audience and accessibility, digital literacy, availability of technological tools, clarity and cultural appeal of messaging can all play a role in the effectiveness with which these messages can be received and perceived by women. It is, therefore, relevant to determine the extent to which digital messages on maternal health play an important role in enhancing maternal health knowledge among women.

It is against this background that this paper focuses on digital maternal health messages to evaluate their efficiency in enhancing the level of women in terms of knowledge about maternal health related issues and how digital communication can be used so as to improve on maternal health awareness and informed practices regarding maternal health issues.

Statement of the Problem

The maternal health is a major health issue facing the populace in Nigeria in spite of the different national and international campaigns to enhance maternal health outcomes. Some of the causes that have attributed to the persistence of maternal mortality and morbidity in the country include lack of accessibility to quality healthcare services, socio-economic factors, cultural practices and poor awareness of maternal health matters by women. Despite the implementation of different maternal health measures, there are still a number of women who are not adequately informed about important maternal health activities like attending prenatal care and knowing the conditions of pregnancy threats, adequate dieting during pregnancy and best postnatal care. These issues have remained persistent to derail the process of enhancing maternal health outcomes and realising sustainable development agenda involving maternal wellbeing.

Access to credible health information is one of the imperative issues that determine the health behaviour of the mother. Lack of knowledge on women regarding maternal health concerns can lead to lower chances of them following stipulated health behaviours that can secure their health conditions and those of their babies. It has been found that maternal health awareness and knowledge are significant to affect the health choices and uptake of maternal healthcare services by women (Ope, 2020; Akokuwebe,

2022). In most communities, there are still disparities in maternal health knowledge which are sometimes attributed to weaknesses in traditional health communication approaches that might not reach all population sections effectively.

The recent years have witnessed the use of digital communication platforms as the avenue of delivering maternal health information to women. With the help of mobile telephones, the social media and other digital technologies, health organisations and communication practitioners can now target a larger audience with the messages on maternal health education. The digital maternal health messages are likely to enhance the level of awareness and knowledge of the women about maternal health practices as they will have timely and accessible information pertaining to the pregnancy and childbirth, as well as, after delivery.

Although there is an increase in the use of digital platforms in communicating maternal health, there are concerns about whether digital maternal health communication messages are effective in positively influencing women in terms of increasing their knowledge on maternal health problems. Although digital technologies provide valid prospects of health information spread, there is need to critically analyse whether exposure to such messages actually improves the understanding of women concerning maternal health practices. As a result, the effectiveness of digital maternal health messages in enhancing maternal health issues among women needs to be studied.

Theoretical Framework

The paper is based on the Health Belief Model and the Diffusion of innovations Theory. The theories are a theoretical foundation to how health promotion messages manipulate the knowledge, perception and behavioural reaction of individuals to health communication. The significance of theories in communication research is that they assist in explaining the relationships between communications processes and human behaviour and this offers a system to understand how a communication message can cause knowledge acquisition and behaviour change (Asemah, 2021).

Health Belief Model

One of the most popular theoretical models in health communication and research on the field of public health is the Health Belief Model (HBM). It was the work of social psychologists with the United States Public Health Service that in the fifties developed the model to explain the failure of individuals to adopt preventive health behaviours or make use of the available health services. The Health Belief Model hypothesises that the perceptions of susceptibility to a health issue, perceived seriousness of health condition, perceived positive effect of preventive action taking and the perceived barrier to the action are four factors that determine the health related behaviour of an individual.

The model suggests that people tend to embrace suggested health behaviours more when they feel that they are exposed to a health issue and have a feeling that the impact of the issue may be dire. Moreover, the people should be convinced that the rewards of performing a certain health behaviour are more than the possible obstacles of

performing the same behaviour. Another factor that is emphasised by the model is the cues to action which are stimuli that prompt people to take preventive health care steps. Such cues can be in form of health education messages, media campaigns and health professional advice.

Digital maternal health messages are potentially used in the context of maternal health communication as triggers to action encouraging women to embrace safe maternal health practices. By receiving digital health information that concerns the health of antenatal care, nutrition during pregnancy, warning signs in pregnancy and postnatal care, women can gain a more efficient insight into the dangers of maternal health and the advantages of following preventive health behaviours. Digital health messages can make an impact and affect the perception of the women and encourage them to make informed health choices during pregnancy and childbirth by enhancing their knowledge and awareness of maternal health issues.

Diffusion of Innovations Theory

The other theoretical approach that applies in this study is the diffusion of innovations theory that was presented by Everett Rogers in 1962. The theory describes the diffusion of new ideas, practices, technologies or innovations in a social system as time goes by. Diffusion according to Rogers is the process in which an innovation is transferred via some channels to the members of a social system. The process of innovation adoption takes place in the form of awareness, interest, evaluation, trial and adoption.

The diffusion of innovations theory recognises communication channels as one of the most important elements in the process of communicating and adopting new ideas. The role of mass media channels, interpersonal communication, as well as digital communication platforms in the dissemination of information on innovations is important. With the help of these communication channels, people get to know about new ideas and can over time embrace them based on how useful they are to them and how they are compatible with other current beliefs and practices they hold.

It can be perceived that digital maternal health messages represent an innovation in maternal health communication, especially in those situations where the traditional health communication strategies can be limited. Mothers can receive their health information promptly through mobile applications, social media, and health applications available digitally and reach wide women populations. Exposing women to these messages could make them conscious of the prescribed maternal health practices and eventually incorporate them into their health behaviour.

The applicability of the diffusion of innovations theory to the current study is that the theory explains how information about maternal health is shared among women through the use of digital communication technologies. Through the use of digital platforms to convey maternal health messages, health organisations and communication practitioners can provide new health knowledge and practices that can shape the knowledge of the women on the issues of maternal health.

Conceptual Review

Electronic Health Communication

Digital health communication is using digital technologies and electronic communication channels to share health information support health education and enable interaction between health providers and the population. As the information and communication technologies developed rapidly, digital platforms like mobile phones, social media, online health portals as well as mobile health applications have gained importance as an avenue of availing health information to different populations. These media make health organisations deliver accessible, interactive and timely health messages to people wherever they are.

The rising adoption of digital technologies in healthcare systems has provided new opportunities to enhance the communications of the population to improve public health and promote the preventative health behaviours. According to Abernethy *et al* (2022), digital health technologies have changed the way healthcare services are being offered by making health-related information more accessible, facilitating communication between patients and healthcare providers, and aiding health education programmes. Digital communication tools have actually become valuable in most developing nations in reaching the sections of the population that might be unable to get the traditional healthcare services.

The use of digital technologies in healthcare communication has been on the growth trend in the Nigerian context with the penetration of the internet and the use of mobile phones spreading throughout the nation. Egwudo *et al* (2025) note that digital health technologies offer great opportunities to the delivery of healthcare and health education in Nigeria and especially in such regions where healthcare infrastructure is underdeveloped. The health institutions and communication practitioners can use digital platforms to spread health messages, offer informational material and promote health-seeking behaviour in the general population.

The digital health communication also enhances the creation of customised health messages with specific information requirements of the specific audience. Bol, Smit & Lustria (2020) believe that individuals should be able to customise their health messages to their requirements and conditions so that the effects of health education interventions would be more beneficial to them. Digital communication platforms used within the scope of maternal health are thus applicable in the delivery of specific maternal health information that impacts women during pregnancy and childbirth with regard to their individual concerns and information requirements.

Electronic Maternal Health Messages

Digital maternal health messages are health-based information associated with pregnancy, childbirth and postnatal information that is shared using digital forms of communication like mobile phones, social media, health apps and other electronic communication methods. The messages will also be meant to enlighten the women about

some key maternal health practices such as antenatal care attendance, prenatal nutrition, danger signs during pregnancy, birth preparedness and postnatal care.

The growing popularity of the digital communication tools as a means of delivering maternal health education can be attributed to the overall trend of digital health communication practices in modern healthcare. Digital maternal health campaigns help the healthcare organisations, governments and development agencies in accessing women with significant health data which could help them to practice safe motherhood. As Mustapha et al. (2021) note, digital interventions of maternal health education have proven a significant potential of enhancing maternal health awareness and knowledge within women, especially when resourceful access to healthcare systems is low.

This has seen social media platforms especially playing a significant role as a medium of conducting maternal health campaigns and health education programmes. According to Abdullahi, Akase & Akpede (2025), social media avenues offer an interactive method of conveying health messages through social media where health practitioners and organisations can share educational content, contact the women and answer questions concerning questions which are related to maternal health issues. With such platforms, maternal health information will be able to reach a broader audience and make women seek the right healthcare services when they are pregnant. However, how well the maternal health communication campaigns is effective will be subject to the exposure of women to health information and their capacity to interpret and use the health information in their lives. Previous research has revealed that mass media and other communication media exposure to health messages is very important in influencing women knowledge on maternal health practices. Indicatively, Adamu (2020) discovered that maternal health risk perception and knowledge among women in rural settings would be greatly determined by their exposure to messages on health communication.

Women's Knowledge of Maternal Health Issues

The knowledge of maternal health issues among women means that they have acquired the necessary knowledge about health information regarding pregnancy, childbirth and after childbirth. The awareness on the proper maternal health practices like visiting the antenatal clinics, the signs of danger in pregnancy, proper nutrition during pregnancy, and seeking the skilled healthcare services during childbirth is among such knowledge.

It is generally known that sufficient awareness of maternal health problems would be essential in enhancing maternal health outcomes. They are able to make informed choices regarding maternal health practices and possible pregnancy complications when women are informed; hence, they tend to pursue timely healthcare services and take preventive health behaviours, which would minimise the risk of maternal morbidity and maternal mortality. Bello et al. (2022) note that maternal health literacy is a major factor that defines how women access maternal healthcare services and outcomes of pregnancy.

In the same manner, empirical findings indicate that maternal health complications knowledge may affect the readiness of women to give birth and capability to identify the early pregnancy indications of health issues. According to Ijdi, Ducille &

Singh (2025), the greater level of maternal health knowledge and awareness among pregnant women can contribute to making informed health choices and requesting proper medical help in case of the need.

The absence of gaps in maternal health knowledge could still be noticed in many developing countries, especially regarding women in rural and underserved communities. Yang et al. (2025) cite that the lack of access to public health services and poor levels of policy awareness are usually the factors that lead to poor levels of maternal health knowledge among women. All these issues demonstrate the need to have effective health communication strategies that will enhance the awareness of women on maternal health concerns.

Communication channels exposing women to health information has demonstrated a significant impact on the awareness of women on the practices of maternal health. Igbinoba et al. (2020) established that maternal health awareness is high in women who receive exposure to health information via mass media channels compared to women who do not receive health information. Therefore, effective communication platforms can be used to enhance the knowledge of women on maternal health issues by increasing their exposure to maternal health messages.

Considering the rising incidence of digital communication technologies, there is a good chance that digital maternal health messages can be utilised to enhance knowledge of women about maternal health problems. Maternal health communication initiatives could help in improving the awareness, knowledge and uptake of recommended maternal health practices through the provision of easy and prompt health information to women via the digital platform.

Role of Digital Communication in Maternal Health Education

Communication has been established to have a positive impact on maternal health awareness and this has found a lot of recognition in the academic world. In the process of conveying health information, the techniques of communication are vital in influencing the awareness of the population about various health matters as well as promoting positive health behaviours. Communication channels in relation to maternal health give an avenue through which women can be able to get the information on antenatal care, complications during pregnancy, safe delivery practices and postnatal care. Researchers note that maternal health information presented by both communication channels contributes greatly to the knowledge that women have on maternal health practices and promotes the use of maternal healthcare services (Igbinoba *et al* 2020; Bello *et al* 2022). As the information and communication technologies are evolving so fast, digital communication platforms have become a potent tool in health education and health promotion. The digital communication technologies like the mobile phone, social media platforms, mobile health applications and online health portals have greatly increased the medium through which health information can be promoted to different populations. These platforms are allowing health organisations and practitioners to give timely, accessible and interactive messages about health to individuals without considering the

geographical locations. As it is explained by Abernethy et al. (2022), digital health technologies have changed the way we communicate in healthcare by making health information more accessible and enhancing communication between healthcare providers and patients.

Digital platforms in the context of maternal health have been more and more used to spread information in the effort to enhance the familiarity of women with maternal health concerns. Digital maternal health messages tend to cover the information about the attendance of antenatal care, prenatal nutrition, the awareness of danger signs during pregnancy and the necessity of skilled attendance at birth. In their systematic review of digital maternal health education interventions based in a low-infrastructure setting, Mustapha *et al* (2021) note that digital communication interventions have already shown strong potential in enhancing maternal health awareness in women, especially in the areas where access to healthcare information might be restricted.

On the same note, digital patient education programmes have also been identified as significant health promotion tools in enhancing maternal knowledge of health and promotion of health-seeking behaviour in expectant mothers. Schnitman *et al* (2022) state that digital health education platforms are convenient in offering maternal health information and help women make suitable decisions regarding pregnancy and childbirth. The digital communication platforms can also help to enhance the knowledge of women on maternal health practices by facilitating uninterrupted access to health information.

Moreover, researchers note that it is crucial to customise health communication messages so that it can be more relevant to the needs and situations of particular target audiences. Individualised digital health communication makes health messages tailored to the nature of individuals, their preferences and information requirements, which improves the efficiency of health education interventions. Bol *et al* (2020) observe that customised health communication practices enhance relevance and efficacy of health communication that may eventually impact the health behaviour and knowledge of individuals.

The growing use of digital technologies in healthcare systems also provided the possibility to develop the scope of maternal health education programmes. Egwudo *et al* (2025) note that digital health technologies can be used to enhance healthcare communication especially in developing nations that might have poor healthcare infrastructure. Using digital communication platforms, health organisations can spread maternal health messages to the masses and can involve women in health education programmes that can help them to achieve better maternal health outcomes.

Moreover, researchers have noted the need to integrate the voice and experiences of women in the maternal health communication programmes. According to Sampson *et al* (2022), perinatal health communication should focus on the voices of mothers and especially mothers at the risk of maternal mortality and morbidity. Incorporating the experiences and information requirements of women, digital maternal health messages can be tailored in a manner that will improve the awareness of women concerning maternal health problems as well as embrace the practices that are suggested on maternal health concerns.

Challenges and Limitations of Digital Maternal Health Communication

Although there are many opportunities linked to digital communication on the issue of maternal health education, researchers have also identified the various challenges and limitations which could be counterproductive to the efficacy of digital maternal health communication. The challenges encompass the problem of digital literacy, technological infrastructure, socio-cultural issues and the plausibility of health information shared over the digital platforms.

The issue of unequal access to digital technologies can be regarded as one of the key problems that are linked to digital communication in maternal health. Even though, the usage of mobile phones and internet services has grown tremendously in most developing nations, there are still inequalities in the access to digital devices and internet access especially in the rural and underserved populations. According to Egwudo *et al* (2025), the poor technological infrastructure and insufficient access to digital technologies could be a barrier to the effective use of digital health interventions in some situations.

The other restriction is associated with the digital literacy of population groups. To be able to access, interpret and apply the information conveyed through digital platforms requires women to possess the capacity of benefiting through digital maternal health messages. Nevertheless, digital illiteracy could lower the success of digital health communication programmes in most communities. Abdullahi *et al* (2025) suggest that, due to poor digital literacy and poor knowledge about digital platforms, women may not be able to participate in the maternal health campaigns done via the social media platform.

Besides the technological and literacy barriers, socio-cultural aspects might also affect the perceptions and reaction of women toward maternal health messages that are conveyed via digital channels of communication. The perceptions of the health risks and responses of health information are usually influenced by cultural beliefs and traditional practices. Adamu (2020) notes that the interpretation of the maternal health messages and the perception of maternal health risks by women, especially in rural societies, can be affected by the cultural practices and social norms.

Moreover, researchers have raised concerns on the accuracy and validity of the health information spread in the digital platform. The interactive and openness of digital communication platforms allow false or misleading information to be quickly dispersed among the users. This misinformation can compromise the process of health communication to mothers and bring confusion to women who want quality and reliable health information. As Mustapha *et al* (2021) observe, despite the good prospects of digital health interventions in providing maternal health education, the success of such interventions is highly dependent on the quality and reliability of the information being shared.

It has also been pointed out by academics that digital maternal health communication should take into account the overall socio-economic conditions of women in developing nations. Poverty, inaccessibility to healthcare facilities and low education

are some of the factors that could affect access and interpretation of maternal health information by women. Yang *et al* (2025) assert that the lack of awareness about health policies and accessibility to publicly provided health services can be the factors that lead to the low rates of maternal health knowledge among women in particular communities.

In addition, the success of the maternal health communication programmes is not merely determined by the availability of information but also on how much the women are able to utilise the knowledge obtained during these communication programmes. Ijdi *et al* (2025) observe that health education campaigns might be successful in raising awareness concerning the health problems of women; even so, behaviour change needs to be maintained over time and health-promoting healthcare settings. This implies that digital maternal health communication is not the sole channel of health communication as it should be an addition to other maternal health education strategies.

In general, despite the great opportunities digital communication technologies present in terms of enhancing maternal health education, it is crucial to deal with the challenges that digital maternal health communication implies to maximise the effects. The provision of equal access to digital technologies and enhancement of digital literacy among women and the formulation of culturally friendly health communication measures are important measures to the effectiveness of digital maternal health messages in increasing knowledge of women to maternal health conditions.

Review of Empirical Studies

There are a few empirical studies that have focused on the correlation between communication exposure and maternal health awareness among women especially in the developing world where maternal mortality has been a major issue in terms of public health. These research papers have examined the role of communication channels like the mass media and the digital platform in informing women about maternal health concerns and their acceptance of the recommended practices in using maternal healthcare.

The research conducted by Igbinoba *et al* (2020) is about the mass media exposure of women and maternal health awareness in Ota, Nigeria. The research involved the way exposure to health information using the channels of communication affected awareness among women on maternal health practices. The results showed that women who regularly received maternal health information in the media had better awareness on the matter of antenatal care, safe birth practices and maternal health complications. It was concluded that health communication messages exposure is an important factor in enhancing the awareness of women on maternal health problems and that greater exposure of women to maternal health information should be disseminated using different communication channels.

On the same note, Adamu (2020) examined how Hausa women were exposed to mass media messages on health and how they viewed cultural practices that influenced maternal health in rural settings of Bauchi State, Nigeria. The researchers concluded that maternal health information through the communication channel made women

understand better the maternal health risks and proper maternal health practices. Nonetheless, the researchers also found out that cultural beliefs and traditional practices at times affected women interpretation of maternal health information. The researcher highlighted the importance of culturally sensitive maternal health communication interventions that will tackle the socio-cultural realities of women in rural communities.

The systematic review by Mustapha *et al* (2021) involved studying digital interventions in maternal health education that take place in low infrastructures. The research conducted an analysis of various digital maternal health education programmes to determine their effect on the knowledge of women on the issue of maternal health. The results were that digital communication tools including mobile health system and mobile messaging system had a significant effect on increasing awareness of women regarding maternal health practices especially in societies where the traditional health education programmes were unavailable. The research also discovered that digital maternal health communication interventions hold a significant potential in enhancing the level of knowledge of maternal health by women.

Bello *et al* (2022) conducted another empirical study where the connection between maternal health literacy and utilisation of maternal healthcare services and pregnancy outcomes in recently born mothers in Nigeria was investigated. The results showed that women who had superior maternal health literacy tended to access maternal healthcare services and embrace recommended maternal health practices. The paper highlighted the importance of improving the knowledge of women on maternal health problems using effective health communication strategies to improve the health outcomes of mothers.

Despite the fact that these studies offer great information regarding the importance of communication in enhancing maternal health awareness among women, most of the existing literature has emphasised more on the traditional mass media exposure and maternal health literacy in general. Although there are studies, which have investigated the digital health education interventions, studies that investigate the effectiveness of the digital messages delivered to mothers on enhancing their knowledge on maternal health issues, especially in the Nigerian setting are still required. This is the reason why the present study aims at adding to the current body of knowledge by investigating how effective digital maternal health messages are in enhancing the knowledge of women on maternal health problems.

Methodology

The research design that was used in this study is the library research design, which allows the researcher to review available scholarly literature and written materials with the view of formulating an overall picture of a research problem. Qualitative research method is based on the use of secondary data to reach a discourse stance (Asemah, Gujbawu, Ekharefo, & Okpanachi, 2017; Arijeniwa, Pepple & Asemah, 2023). Under this strategy, the research used secondary sources in the form of books, magazines, newspapers, journal articles and chapters in edited books, which were pertinent to the

research topic of digital health communication, maternal health education and maternal health issues knowledge among women. The study adopted a thematic approach to the data analysis of the data collected through the reviewed literature which included the identification and arrangement of critical themes in the materials as per the objectives of the research.

Digital Communication as a Tool for Improving Maternal Health Knowledge

The increased role of digital communication in maternal health education can be perceived as one of the central themes of the literature reviewed. Digital technology has provided new avenues through which health information can be shared among women using mobile phones and the social media as well as health applications and other web applications. The digital communication tools offer available avenues through which maternal health information can be communicated to women irrespective of the geographical boundaries.

The available academic literature supports the notion that digital health communication can be used to enhance the knowledge of women about maternal health conditions through the delivery of timely and relevant health-related information. An example study by Mustapha *et al* (2021) showed that the efficacy of digital maternal health education interventions greatly enhanced the maternal health awareness of the low-infrastructure setting women. Likewise, Schnitman *et al* (2022) found out that digital patient education platforms increase the knowledge of women on health issues related to pregnancy and enable them to make informed choices during pregnancy and childbirth.

One more theory which explains why digital communication is effective in maternal health education is the Diffusion of Innovations Theory, according to which a new idea and practice are disseminated through communication channels in a social system. In this regard, the digital solutions have been used as a medium through which women can be informed about maternal health and the best practices to embrace in order to improve their health. Being exposed to such knowledge causes the women to be more knowledgeable about the maternal health practices and might eventually engage in them as a part of the health behaviour.

Effect of Maternal Health Messages Exposure on Women Awareness

Another theme that come up as a result of the literature examined is the high contribution of communication exposure in enhancing maternal health issues knowledge between women. Some of the studies have shown that the women who are exposed to the maternal health messages, when using communication channels, are more likely to be more aware of the maternal health practices. Health information exposes the women to more information and resources about the dangers associated with pregnancy, which promotes the women to seek relevant maternal healthcare services.

As an example, Igbino *et al* (2020) noted that women who were exposed to maternal health messages in media outlets exhibited a higher level of awareness on antenatal care, safe child delivery methods and maternal health complications. On the

same note, Bello *et al* (2022) documented that maternal health literacy is one of the major contributors of maternal healthcare service utilisation and pregnancy outcomes among women. These results indicate that a successful communication of maternal health information can increase maternal health practices awareness and a safer maternal health behaviour among women.

Health Belief Model of health behaviour explains this relationship between health behaviour and exposure to information further. The model suggests that people tend to be more inclined towards preventive health behaviours when they are knowledgeable of the risks of having a health condition and other associated benefits of taking preventive action. The digital maternal health messages are thus action signals that encourage the women to use the recommended maternal health behaviours by raising their levels of awareness of maternal health hazards and the advantages of using healthcare properly.

Structural and Socio-Cultural Constraints Affecting Digital Maternal Health Communication

Although digital maternal health communication could have beneficial effects, structural and socio-cultural barriers that could restrain the success of digital maternal health messages are also mentioned in the reviewed literature. Poor access to digital technologies has been cited to be among the greatest challenges. Inequality in mobile phone access and the internet continues to be high in most developing nations, especially in the rural and underserved regions.

Egwudo *et al* (2025) observe that a shortage of technological infrastructure and disparities in access to digital technologies may negatively affect the success of the digital health communication programmes in some communities. On the same note, Abdullahi *et al.* (2025) state that low digital literacy among certain groups of people could influence the capacity of women to retrieve and understand maternal health messages posted online.

The socio-cultural forces are also significant in the formation of the reaction of women to the maternal health communication. Adamu (2020) noted that cultural beliefs and practices tend to affect the way women perceive maternal health messages and the perception of maternal health risks. Certainly, in some societies, strong cultural values can prevent women to embrace some maternal health practices despite their access to health information. These results can imply that even though digital maternal health communication has the potential to enhance maternal health awareness, the success of these methods relies on the broader structural and socio-cultural context which has an impact on how women receive information and perceive health messages. Digital maternal health communication efforts must therefore be culturally sensitive, accessible, and inclusive that can have positive impact in enhancing knowledge of maternal health issues among women.

Conclusion

It has been discovered that digital communication is a significant instrument of spreading maternal health information and enhancing the understanding of maternal health

problems among women. The literature reviewed has shown that exposure to maternal health messages via digital platforms like mobile phones, social media, and other digital platforms, can help increase the awareness of the women regarding maternal health practices, including antenatal care, safe delivery and postnatal care. The prospects of digital maternal health communication are thus vast in extending access to maternal health information, especially where the traditional health communication features might be ineffective in reaching a larger population. Nevertheless, the success of digital maternal health messages can depend on such factors as digital literacy, access to digital technologies, and socio-cultural factors. These factors are critical in maximising the effects of digital maternal health communication to enhance the knowledge of women on maternal health issues. The following are the recommendations based on the foregoing:

- a. The government agencies and organisations working in the field of health should incorporate digital communication methods in maternal health education programmes to increase access of women to maternal health information.
- b. The community-based interventions must be set in place to enhance the digital literacy level of women in order to empower them to access, comprehend and use digital-based disseminated maternal health information.
- c. The effectiveness of digital maternal health messages can be made to reflect the cultural need and realities of women in various communities through designing maternal health communication campaigns.

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